

DYES DERIVED FROM SUCCINIC AND MALEIC ACID AND THEIR DERIVATIVES AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS

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A comparative study has been made between the applicability of dyes obtained from succinic and derived succinic acids and the corresponding dyes from maleic acids as adsorption indicators in argentometric titrations. It has been shown that whereas succinic acid derivatives—resorcinol succinein and itaconein—serve as very useful indicators, the corresponding dyes from maleic acid do not have any applicability. The behaviour has been explained on the existing theories of colour and of adsorption indicators. As a result of the investigation, a new adsorption indicator, resorcinol itaconein, has been described.

Since the discovery of Fajans (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1923, 29, 495), an extensive study has been made of the dyes derived from phthalic acid, *o*-sulphobenzoic acid and a few other dyes as adsorption indicators in argentometric titrations. No attempt seems to have been made to make a systematic study of the suitability of the corresponding dyes derived from the other dibasic acids as adsorption indicators. In recent communications from these laboratories, the applicability of the dyes derived from succinic acid (Mehrotra, Tewari and Dube, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 165), quinolinic and cinchomeric acids (Mehrotra, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1946, 15, 148) has been described. It has been shown that resorcinol succinein is a very suitable indicator for the argentometric titrations of chloride, bromide and iodide ions and in certain cases, it works even better than the classical adsorption indicator, fluorescein. It was considered of interest to try the applicability of maleic acid derivatives as adsorption indicator and to compare the applicability of resorcinol malein with that of the succinein. On finding the inapplicability of resorcinol malein as adsorption indicator in argentometric titrations, the comparison has been extended to two isomeric dyes, resorcinol itaconein (methylene-succinein) and resorcinol citraconein (methyl-malein) and similar results have been obtained in their case also.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Dyes.—Resorcinol succinein and malein were prepared as described by Sheshadri and co-workers (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 26A, 308).

Resorcinol itaconein and citraconein were prepared by the method of Dhar and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 5, 247, 253).

Resorcinol malein as Adsorption Indicator.—A 0.2% solution of the dye was prepared in alcohol and used as adsorption indicator in this investigation.

When the chloride solution (about *N*/10) is titrated against silver ions, the coagulation of the silver chloride occurs a little before the equivalent point and the dye is adsorbed on the precipitate. However, the colour developed on the particles due to the adsorption of the dye is not bright and does not differ markedly from the colour of the dye in suspension, and hence the end-point is not sharp.

In the case of thiocyanate ions, the coagulation of the precipitate begins quite early and at the equivalent point, the particles adsorb the dye with the development a slight pink colour. The colour developed both in the case of the chloride and the

thiocyanate is much less intense than in the case when succinein is used in the place of malein as indicator.

In the case of bromide and iodide ions, a very sharp and well defined colour change of yellow to pink has been described to occur when resorcinol succinein is used as an adsorption indicator. However, when resorcinol malein is used as indicator in place of the succinein, no perceptible colour change occurs on the coagulated particles.

Resorcinol Itaconein and Citraconein as Adsorption Indicators

Resorcinol itaconein and resorcinol citraconein are two isomeric dyes having the following constitutions :

Resorcinol itaconein.

Resorcinol citraconein.

The itaconein may be said to be a derivative of succinic acid, whereas the citraconein is a derivative of the maleic acid. It is of interest to observe that similar to the comparative behaviour of resorcinol succinein and malein as adsorption indicators, itaconein gives very sharp end-points and is a very suitable indicator for the argentometric titration of the chloride, bromide, iodide and thiocyanate ions, whereas the citraconein does not give sharp end-points in the titration of halide ions.

Titration of Chloride Ions against Silver Ions.—When chloride ions are titrated against silver nitrate using resorcinol itaconein (0.2% solution) as indicator, a very sharp colour change, colorless to pink, occurs at the equivalent point. When the solutions have a concentration of about $N/10$, the coagulation occurs before the end-point, but the particles remain white so long as the chloride ions are present in excess in the supernatant liquid, and develop a bright pink colour as soon as the silver ions become in slight excess. In the case of dilute solutions (about $N/100$), the coagulation of the silver chloride does not occur and a sharp colour change (light pink to deep pink) occurs in the suspension phase itself. With resorcinol itaconein as adsorption indicator, the chloride ions can be titrated with very sharp end-points up to a dilution of $N/100$.

The colour change is not at all sharp, when in the above titration resorcinol citraconein (0.2% solution in alcohol) is used as an adsorption indicator in the place of the itaconein. In the more concentrated solutions, the colour developed on the particles is much less in intensity than in the case of the itaconein. In the case of dilute solutions (about $N/100$), coagulation of the silver chloride does not occur, but there is no sharp colour change at any stage. The colour of the suspension goes on becoming

more and more pink as the silver nitrate solution is run in, but there no perceptible colour change occurring sharply at any stage.

Titration of Thiocyanate Ions.—When the thiocyanate ions (about $N/10$) are titrated against silver nitrate (about $N/10$) solution, using resorcinol itaconein as adsorption indicator, coagulation of the silver thiocyanate begins quite early, but the particles remain colorless so long as the thiocyanate ions are present in excess and assume a bright pink colour just at the equivalent point. The titrations can be carried out up to a dilution of $N/200$ with very sharp end-points; in the more dilute solutions the colour change (colorless to pink) occurs in the apparently homogeneous suspension phase.

In the case when resorcinol citraconein is used as the indicator in place of the itaconein, the colour developed on the particles is much lighter and so the end-point is much less sharp.

Titrations of Bromide and Iodide Ions.—Using resorcinol itaconein as adsorption indicator, bromide and iodide ions can be titrated with very sharp and well defined end-points. In the case of the bromide ions the colour change at the end-point is from colorless or pale yellow to bright pink and very sharp end-points are obtained up to a dilution of $N/250$. The colour change in the case of iodide ions is from yellow to bright pink and titrations are possible up to a dilution of $N/500$ solutions.

When citraconein is used as adsorption indicator, the colour change is not at all sharp in the case of bromide ions. However, in the case of iodide ions the end-point is sufficiently sharp and the colour change occurs from yellow to pink, though the pink shade developed in the case of citraconein is much less bright than in the case of itaconein under identical conditions. Using citraconein as indicator, the colour change at the end-point is not sharp in dilutions greater than $N/100$.

The following table records a few of the results of the titrations carried out with the help of a microburette using a 0.2% solution of resorcinol itaconein as adsorption indicator.

TABLE I

Conc. of halide soln. (5 c.c.)	Drops of Indicator.	Conc of AgNO_3 soln.	Transition of colour.	Remarks.
$N/10\text{-KCl}$	2	5 to 5.02 c.c. of $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$	White ppt. $\rightarrow$ pink ppt.	The coagulation of the silver chloride particles begins much earlier. The colour change though occurring on coagulated particles is very sharp and quite reversible.
$N/100\text{-KCl}$	2	„	Light pink susp. $\rightarrow$ deep pink susp.	The coagulation of the ppt. does not occur. The colour change occurs in the apparently homogeneous phase and is quite reversible.
$N/10\text{-KBr}$	2	4.99 to 5.01 c.c. of $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$	Pale yellow ppt $\rightarrow$ pink ppt.	The end-point is very sharp and quite reversible.
$N/250\text{-KI}$	2	5 to 5.02 c.c. of $N/250\text{-AgNO}_3$	White susp. $\rightarrow$ pink susp.	The end-point is very sharp. The coagulation of the ppt. occurs a few seconds afterwards and the ppt. is pink coloured, changing to black very rapidly.
$N/10\text{-KI}$	2	„	Yellow ppt. $\rightarrow$ pink ppt.	Very very sharp end-point. Colour change reversible.
$N/500\text{-KI}$	2	5 to 5.03 c.c. of $N/500\text{-AgNO}_3$	Yellow susp. $\rightarrow$ pink susp.	No coagulation. The colour change occurs in the apparently homogeneous phase.

DISCUSSION

It is of interest to observe as the above investigation demonstrates that whereas resorcinol derivatives of succinic acids and acids derived from it serve as very suitable adsorption indicators, the corresponding dyes derived from maleic acid do not show any sharp colour change on the particles. In a number of communications, Dutt and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2524), Tewari and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 3, 60) and Dhar and Dutt (*ibid.*, 1927, 4, 247, 253) have shown that the dyes derived from maleic acid and its derivatives have a deeper colour than the corresponding dyes from succinic acid. This increment in absorption, they have explained to be due to the introduction of double bond which hinders free rotation in the molecule. Fajans and Hassel (*loc. cit.*) have explained the colour change occurring in the adsorption indicators to be due to the deformation of the electron shell that the dye ions undergo when they are in the force fields of oppositely charged and neighbouring ions. This deformability may be expected to be less in the dyes with a double bond than with the dyes having no double bond and hence no restricted rotation. The simple qualitative explanation explains very easily the observed marked difference between the dyes derived from succinic and maleic acids.

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